

NORMAL SUBGROUPS OF INDEX 8 IN THE GROUP REPRESENTATION OF THE CAYLEY TREE

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Many papers and books have been written on the theory of groups. However, there are still unsolved problems, many of which arise in fields such as physics, biology, and other natural sciences. For example, when the configuration of a physical system is defined on a lattice (which can be viewed as a graph of a group), the configuration may be interpreted as a function defined over the lattice. Numerous studies have explored different types of partitions in groups (lattices) (see for example [1]-[3]).

Let G_k represent a free product of $k + 1$ cyclic groups of order two, with generators a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k+1} . The group G is assumed to have a finite number of generators of order two, and let r represent the minimum number of such generators for G . Without loss of generality, we can designate these generators as b_1, b_2, \dots, b_r . Additionally, let e_1 denote the identity element of G . We then define a homomorphism from G_k onto G .

Let $\Xi_n = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$ be a partition of the set $N_k \setminus A_0$, where $0 \leq |A_0| \leq k + 1 - n$. The homomorphism $u_n : \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k+1}\} \rightarrow \{e_1, b_1, \dots, b_m\}$ is then given by the following expression:

$$u_n(x) = \begin{cases} e_1, & \text{if } x = a_i, i \in A_0 \\ b_j, & \text{if } x = a_i, i \in A_j, j = \overline{1, n} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

For any element $b \in G$, we define $R_b[b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m]$ as a representation of the word b in terms of the generators b_1, b_2, \dots, b_r , with $r \leq m$. The homomorphism $\gamma_n : G \rightarrow G$ is defined by the formula:

$$\gamma_n(x) = \begin{cases} e_1, & \text{if } x = e_1 \\ b_i, & \text{if } x = b_i, i = \overline{1, r} \\ R_{b_i}[b_1, \dots, b_r], & \text{if } x = b_i, i \neq \overline{1, r} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Theorem. For the group G_k following statement is hold

$$\{H \mid H \text{ is a normal subgroup of } G_k \text{ with } |G_k : H| = 10\} = \\ = \{H_{B_0 B_1 B_2}^{(5)}(R_{10}) \mid B_1, B_2 \text{ is a partition of the set } N_k \setminus B_0\}.$$

Reference:

1. Ganikhodjaev, N.N., Rozikov, U.A., (1997), Description of periodic extreme Gibbs measures of some lattice model on the Cayley tree, Theor.Math.Phys. 111, pp. 480-486.
2. U.A., Rozikov, F.H., Haydarov., (2014), Normal subgroups of finite index for the group representation of the Cayley tree, TWMS Jour.Pure.Appl.Math. 5, pp. 234-240.
3. U.A., Rozikov., (2013) Gibbs measures on a Cayley trees, World Sci. Pub, Singapore. Normal Subgroups of Index 8 in the Group Representation of the Cayley Tree

